

PHRASAL VERBS AND THEIR MEANINGS IN PRIDE AND PREJUDICE

Nigora Khudoykulova

Students of Termez state university 3-course(Termez,Uzbekistan)

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7147719>

Annotation: At a time when the volume and quality of data are increasing as a result of the development of modern technologies, it is also important to choose from the given data the ones that are necessary and easy to use. The field of English is very rich and it can be difficult to organize and receive the information in it in a short time. Today we are going to talk about phrasal verbs as one of the most problematic and controversial topics in English. Although phrasal verbs appear to be very complex and difficult to learn from, it is actually easier to memorize phrasal verbs by organizing the connections between meaning and structure between them. It can be seen that in many literary books the writer has also skillfully used phrasal verbs with his skill, and we can memorize phrasal verbs more quickly and reliably by reading these books.

KEY WORDS: phrasal verb, novelism, pride and prejudice, Jane Austen, mind and sense, definition.

INTRODUCTION: In this article we will talk not only about phrasal verbs but also about their meanings. Memorizing phrasal verbs is not only easy but also a fun exercise in the way that we want to advise. In this case, it is necessary to pay special attention to the skill of English writers in the use of phrasal verbs, because the ability to use phrasal verbs correctly and in their proper place testifies to the skill of the writer. Phrasal verbs are available in many languages and their meanings are translated from one language to another, so the translation of phrasal verbs can cause great difficulty and confusion when translating rare works of English into other languages. Because phrasal verbs don't just mean one thing, they can have multiple and even dozens of meanings. For example, the word go away has several meanings

1) To leave a place or person. Example: She angrily told him to go away and stop bothering her.

2) To leave home for a period of time. Example: They are going away on vacation.

3) To stop existing or happening. Example: I just wish there was some way to make the pain go away. [merriam-webster.com]

MATERIALS AND DISCUSSION: In the article we will talk about the phrasal verbs included in the book "Pride and Prejudice", which belongs to Jane Austin, the beloved author of the English people, and used in writing this book. We learn phrasal verbs and their usage by reading books in English. Jane Austen was born on December 16, 1775, and died on July 18, 1817. She is an English writer who lived and worked

in the 19th century. She is the author of many books on aristocracy. Her works made her one of the most famous and beloved writers of English literature. She is considered one of the great figures of English novelism. Citizenship: United Kingdom of Great Britain and Ireland and Great Britain. Profession: writer. Father: George Austen, mother: Cassandra Austen. Education- Reading Abbey Girls School. Years of activity: 1787 - 1817. Austen's work criticizes sentimental novels written in the late 18th century and is part of a transition to 19th century realism. In her works, she describes ordinary people in everyday life. This gave the English novel a distinctive modern character. Austen's stories are often humorous, but they also show that women's social status and economic security depend on their marriage. Her works are also about moral issues. "Pride and Prejudice" was written by English author Jane Austen, who began writing the novel in 1796. But the novel saw the light of publishing in 1813 because publishers rejected the manuscript, and it lay under the fabric for more than fifteen years. Following the success of "Sense and Sensibility", published in 1811, Jane Austen finally published her first work. The play tells the story of Elizabeth Bennet's adventures and horrible mistakes. Focusing on Elizabeth's character, the author introduces us to society through humor and reveals her flaws as well. This was in keeping with the image of the protagonist in his time. The unique relationship between Elizabeth and Darcy is undoubtedly the most remarkable part of the work, as it engages the reader throughout the story, a relationship that goes through extremely confusing stages and eventually accepts love. While many consider Austen's work to be romantic, the author seems to have moved away from the love story she chose. The protagonists stumble, make mistakes. It's a real idea of what can lead to a romantic relationship between two people, in which not everything will turn out the way we want. Through this work of the great writer it is possible to study the phrasal verbs in English. That is, it is possible to find phrasal verb meanings along with reading and memorize them while reading, rather than marking or underlining phrasal verbs during reading. 1) He came down on Monday to see the place and was so pleased with it that he agreed to take possession immediately, and that some of his servants are to be in the house by the end of the week. [9.2] 2) "So it is," cried her mother "I and Mrs Long do not come back until the day before, so it will be impossible for her to introduce him, because she will not know him herself." [11.2] 3) Turning round, he looked for a moment at Elizabeth and then he looked away and said: "She is fairly pretty, but not good-looking enough." [14.2] 4) Elizabeth accepted their company, and the three young ladies set off together.

[19. 2]

5)I have, therefore, made up my mind to tell you that I do not want to dance; and now, think badly of me if you dare. [22.2] 6)Lady Catherine listened to half a song and then talked to her other nephew, until Darcy walked away from her, and, moving towards the piano, positioned himself so that he had a view of the performer's face. [47.2] 7)Yes-if Darcy does not put it off again. I share with him the responsibility of looking after Miss Darcy. [49.2] 8)Her aunt and uncle set out on a walk, leaving her to enjoy them in quiet. [63.2] 9)He turned back with them, and walked towards the house. [69.2] 10) A look from Jane begged Elizabeth to remain, but when, some moments later, the door half opened and her mother called out that she wanted her, she was forced to go. [79.2] Here are some of the phrasal verbs listed in the book above, and by reading this book we will learn about phrasal verbs, their meaning and use, which make it easier to learn a language and especially one of the most problematic topics

CONCLUSION: In summary, memorizing phrasal verbs by definition and memorizing phrasal verbs by reading art bees is a very effective and convenient method. Especially for beginners, this method helps a lot to increase pronunciation and vocabulary. As an easy way to learn phrasal verbs, it is recommended to read a book and read phrasal verbs from books with special attention. Reading a book every day not only helps in language learning but also develops worldview and can help to improve all skills. Hundreds of phrasal verbs can be cited in the book "Pride and Prejudice" itself, and their meanings should be seen through additional books, and thus spirituality can be enhanced. This work has been recognized by hundreds of book lovers, so it will not bore the reader and make the process of reading a book not only necessary but also a fun activity

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